

Increasing Tourism Image through the Tourism Marketing Development Program Implementation in Bandung City

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ABSTRACT: This study describes the implementation of a marketing development program by the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City to increase the tourism destination image, which impacts the increasing number of tourist visits and local revenue. However, this program is different from what was expected. The research employs a qualitative approach and data collection methods using observation, interviews, documents, and literature studies. The research uses data analysis techniques with three stages: data condensation, data presentation, and conclusion and verification. The results of this study indicate that the implementation of the tourism marketing development program by the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung has not been run optimally in terms of the program's implementation elements and environmental factors. From the standpoint of the program overview, the budget and infrastructure facilities are still inadequate. From the implementation aspect, the process of implementation lacks employees, and cooperation with tourism partners has not gone well. Moreover, on the environmental part, many social issues still occur in the surrounding community that affects the implementation of the program.

KEYWORDS: program implementation, tourism marketing, tourism image

INTRODUCTION

Tourism development is one of the areas that must be prioritized to realize its full potential. It is due to the tendency of tourism to become a leading sector, especially by increasing the people's and the government's income. The World Tourism Organization says that the tourism industry has very bright prospects and will grow with an average growth rate of 4.2% per year; the regions that will experience the largest growth rate are countries in Asia, including Indonesia (Sedarmayanti, 2005).

Indonesia is a country with abundant natural resources and has the potential to be processed and utilized, including various kinds of tourism potential with various tribes, customs, cultures, and historical heritage. What is no less interesting is the beauty of its natural panorama, which has quite the potential to be developed in the tourism sector. The development of tourism in Indonesia is one of the focuses that need to be optimized to maximize its potential, due to the tendency of tourism to become a leading sector. The main reasons for developing tourism in a tourist destination locally, regionally, or nationally are very closely related to regional or national development (Yoeti, 2016). If managed properly, tourism can significantly increase the economy of a region, especially by generating foreign exchange and increasing the income of the community and the government (Chairunisalda, 2021)

In managing tourism, the government has the authority to regulate all tourism policies, such as tourism management and organization. Following Law Number 10 of 2009 concerning tourism, there has been a shift in policy direction in which local governments have the right and authority to regulate and manage tourism affairs in their territory. For this reason, local governments must be able to provide concrete evidence that can be felt by the community in developing existing tourism.

The Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City has authority over all tourism affairs in the city. According to Article 2 of Bandung Mayor Regulation Number 1398 of 2016 concerning the position, organizational structure, duties and functions, and work procedures of the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City, the Service is a component executor of government affairs that organizes the fields of culture and tourism. Being the hub of community activities in West Java, Bandung has emerged as the key entry point for numerous sources of economic growth in the region. Additionally, the tourist industry is one of the drivers of economic expansion. Bandung in West Java has developed into an image of a national tourism development area through various locations (Yuaningsih, 2021). The phrase "where the wonders of West Java begin" refers to Bandung as the gateway to the region's magnificent tourist attractions.

Therefore, an image can be understood as an impression of an object based on one's knowledge of or experience with the thing from one's environment or other parties. We can infer that the "tourism image" refers to visitors' perceptions of the attractions they see, which may affect their decision to return (Muniroh et al., 2020). Initiatives for tourism marketing development aim to increase the number of tourist visits and increase regional budget income. Consequently, the perception of tourism might have an impact on both outcomes. However, Bandung's tourist industry and municipal economy have suffered in recent years due to COVID-19. Figure 1 below depicts the anticipated number of tourist visits from 2017 to 2021:

Figure 1: Number of tourist arrivals

Source: Research findings, 2022

According to Figure 1, there were comparatively more visitors to Bandung between 2017 and 2019. In contrast, Bandung will see fewer visitors in 2020–2021. In 2020, there will be about 3.259.300 visitors, a drop of 61.99%, or 5.267.962, from the 8,497,052 visitors in 2019. The number of tourists arriving in 2021 will remain significantly lower than in the previous year. The drop in visitors has harmed the local economy's reliance on tourism-related earnings. The tourism industry's contribution to municipal tax income from 2018 to 2021 is shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2: The contribution of the tourism sector to local revenue

Source: Research findings, 2022

Figure 2 shows that, compared to 2019, when original regional revenue was IDR 771,491,783,780, or USD 51.217.671, the decline in actual regional revenue in 2020 was approximately 50.7%, or IDR 379,603,938,819, or USD 25.201.084. The decrease in the number of foreign and domestic tourist arrivals is another clear indicator of the pandemic's influence on the tourism industry. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic has afflicted up to 7,600 tourist players from various sectors, including the hospitality business and the creative industry (Budianto, 2021). The government of Bandung City must work to counteract the pandemic's effects on the tourism industry. The Culture and Tourism Office is attempting to implement a marketing development program. The goal of marketing in the tourism sector is to determine visitors' needs and wants and provide them with travel options that meet

those needs and want (Revida et al., 2020). Tourists will be interested in taking vacations if effective tourism marketing meets the needs, desires, and expectations of tourists.

This program was carried out a lot to strengthen the image of tourism, so it is expected that it can increase the number of tourist visits and the receipt of local revenue. However, in practice, the researcher found indications of problems in the tourism marketing development program. Less optimal cooperation with tourism partners in tourism marketing. This is because meetings with tourism partners are carried out online so sometimes there are frequent miscommunications which lead to unclear information involvement and the expected implementation of the collaboration is not achieved. In addition, in the process of establishing cooperation with tourism partners, is ineffective and inflexible so several tourism partners. Furthermore, there are inadequate existing facilities to support the implementation of tourism marketing development programs. The availability of facilities such as computers is very limited, with inadequate specifications, and not following the number of existing employees. Expert staff in the field of promotion activities need adequate computer facilities, cameras, broadcasting studios, tripods, and other facilities to make graphic designs, edit videos, and develop ideas to produce audio-visual works needed in tourism promotion activities. And lastly, the budget provided is not sufficient to carry out tourism marketing development programs. In this case, the budget provided is not following the needs in terms of the cost of activities in the program implemented, especially in tourism promotion. Therefore, in this study, researchers consider it important to explore the implementation of tourism marketing development programs.

METHOD

Qualitative methods are used to explore and understand the significance of individuals or groups in human or social problems (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). This study methodology involves various questions, procedures, and data collected from participants. The researcher underneath comprehensive information regarding the implementation of the Tourism Marketing Development Program, designed to improve the image of tourism to increase the number of tourist visits and increase local revenue. The obtained data source consists of both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected directly from the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City, and secondary data were collected from relevant literature, journals, and other sources. The data was collected via observations, interviews, documents, and relevant literature studies.

Interviews were conducted with key informants at the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City, which consisted of sub-sections of programs, data, and information, heads of promotion sections, heads of marketing analysis sections, heads of tourism cooperation sections, tourism promotion section staff, marketing analysis section staff, tourism cooperation section staff, and tourism information center experts. Field research was carried out over a period of six months, from June to November 2022. Through the observations made, researchers can re-examine or complete the data and information obtained from interviews conducted or the study of documents and archives to obtain further information and a description of the conditions that occurred happened in the field.

Triangulation is a technique for checking the validity of data by examining evidence originating from these sources and using it to build a coherent justification for the theme (Creswell, 2018). Furthermore, Cresswell suggested that there are three types of triangulations, consisting of source triangulation, technical triangulation, and time triangulation. In this research, the researcher used source triangulation to test the credibility of the data by checking data regarding the implementation of tourism marketing development programs obtained from several sources and described. This study uses the guidance of program implementation theory which consists of program overview, target groups, program implementation element, and environmental factors for describes the program implementation the tourism marketing development program implementation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. PROGRAM OVERVIEW

In the implementation process, it is necessary to have a program to be implemented. To find out what kind of program will be implemented, it is necessary to have clear foundations, goals, and objectives to be achieved, as well as an adequate budget and facilities. With the clarity of the foundation, goals, and objectives to be achieved, as well as an adequate budget and facilities, the

implementation of the program can also run optimally. An adequate budget and facilities are factors supporting the success of the program's implementation (Tachjan, 2006).

a. Program Principles, Goals, And Objectives

The program principles are the guideline for various program implementation activities. The program's principles are required for program implementation so that the actions or activities are directed and produce results according to the program's goals and objectives. Based on the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City Strategic Plan for 2018–2023, the principle of this program is to realize the vision and mission of the Bandung city government. As one of the regional apparatuses in Bandung city, as stipulated in the Regional Regulation of the Bandung City Number 8 of 2016, the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City, as the organizer of cultural and tourism affairs, carries out or becomes a tool for achieving the vision that supports the achievement of the mission of the Bandung City. In its implementation, the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City has programs and activities. One of them is the tourism marketing development program. The tourism marketing development program has goals and objectives to improve the tourism image of Bandung City. Strengthening the tourism image of Bandung City is expected to increase local revenue and tourist visits.

b. Program Budget

The budget needs to be considered so that the implementor can determine and ensure that the program's needs can be met and utilized to overcome existing problems. The importance of the budget in program implementation has always been the focus of attention for the government and other stakeholders (Lecesnawati & Prabawati, 2017). The regional government of Bandung City funds tourism activities for the Culture and Tourism Office through a budget sourced from the Regional Expenditure Budget of Bandung City. In 2021, the Regional Government of Bandung City will provide a budget for tourism activities of 38,664,347,930 IDR or 2.566.842 USD. The budget is directed to carry out all tourism affairs at the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City, where these matters constitute the entire program compiled by the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City. Of the total available budget, the tourism marketing development program has a budget of IDR 2,682,982,375 or an estimated 176,943 USD. The tourism marketing development program only gets a budget allocation of 7% of the total available budget for tourism activities at the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City. Based on the interviews that the researcher has conducted, they have found that the available budget is insufficient for all marketing development program activities. As seen from quite a few sub-activities, the available budget cannot be sufficient for each implementation of the activities in the marketing development program. In Figure 2, it can be seen that the general funding for several activities in the marketing development program is as follows:

Figure 3. Program Budget of Tourism Marketing Development

Source: The Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City Work Plan, 2021

According to Figure 3, tourism promotion activities receive a larger budget compared to other activities in the marketing development program. This is appropriate because tourism promotion activities have higher performance targets compared to other activities in this program. However, based on interviews conducted, the available budget is not sufficient to carry out tourism promotion activities. This budget shortage was felt several years ago, even before the COVID-19 pandemic, until 2021, although in the end the promotion section still tried to carry out tourism promotion but could not cover 100% of promoting all tourism activities in the Bandung City in its implementation because it was adjusted with the available budget. Some of the sub-activities that have not been optimally fulfilled in tourism promotion are digital marketing on social media; this is due to the absence of account codes for promotion budgeting through social media and an insufficient budget for organizing events.

The marketing development program has four activities with predetermined achievement targets in the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City Work Plan for 2021. It can be seen in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1. Activities Tourism Marketing Development Program in 2021

No	Activity	Description	Performance Achievement Targets
1	Tourism Promotion Activities	Number of Tourism Promotion Activities	150 Promotion Activities
2	Marketing Cooperation Development Activities	Number of Cooperation Activities Strengthening tourism marketing	20 Cooperation agreement
3	Tourism market analysis activities	Number of Tourism Market Analysis Study Documents	10 Analysis Study Documents
4	Information Technology Utilization Activities for Tourism Development	Number of updated tourism marketing information systems	5 Information Systems

Source: The Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City Work Plan, 2021

Figure 3 and Table 1 show that tourism promotion activities in this program receive a larger budget than other activities in the marketing development program. This is appropriate because tourism promotion activities are activities that have more performance achievement targets compared to other activities in this program. However, the available budget is insufficient each year to carry out tourism promotion activities. Based on interviews with informants, he explained that this budget shortfall occurred from a few years ago until 2021. So that the activities carried out by the marketing sector, especially tourism promotion activities, have not been able to cover all the things needed in marketing in Bandung City, one of which is not yet there is a budget for digital marketing promotions and a lack of budget for exhibitions and organizing tourism events.

As a result, less-than-ideal activities may be carried out due to the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City’s limited budget. This is further supported by the claim that, according to a survey, the amount of money allocated from the regional budget for revenue and expenditure to the tourism sector in Indonesia is still quite low (Revida et al., 2020), Particularly in the field of tourism marketing, which has an impact on the implementation of tourism marketing activities.

c. Program Facilities

Apart from the availability of a sufficient budget, facilities are also factors supporting the success of program implementation. Without adequate facilities, it will be difficult for the executors of the marketing development program to achieve the goals and objectives that have been set. These facilities can be in the form of vehicle facilities, computer facilities, or other facilities that can support program implementation. The facilities available to support tourism marketing development programs are inadequate and very limited. In computer facilities, there is a large comparison between the number of employees and the available computers, this can be seen in Figure 4

Figure 4. Comparison of the Number of Computer Facilities and the Number of Employees in Each Section

Source: Research findings, 2022

In Figure 4, it can be seen that many employees do not have adequate facilities; around 60% of employees in the marketing sub-section do not have a computer to work with. Based on interviews with computer informants who are important in supporting the implementation of this program, computer deficiencies can hinder the work carried out by employees, especially if other work needs to be done at the same time. Apart from computers, the marketing sub-section only has one camera and one printer, even though tourism marketing is very close to the digital world, especially during a pandemic. For this reason, in carrying out the program, supporting facilities such as a studio, camera, mic, tripod, lighting, etc. are needed. Therefore, consideration is needed to ensure the availability of facilities needed to carry out activities in the marketing development program so that the implementation of each activity will be even better.

II. TARGET GROUPS

In a program that will be implemented, there are community groups that receive the impact of the implementation of the program. This is what is called the target group. Target groups can also be interpreted as those who are required to adapt to new patterns by interacting with the program being implemented or as groups of people who are affected by the existence of a program. In line with this, (Tachjan, 2006) also explained that the communication factor greatly influences program acceptance by the target group, so when the communication process does not go well, this will become a weak point in achieving program implementation effectiveness. Thus, disseminating program contents through a good communication process will affect the program implementation process.

Tourists are the target audience for the tourism marketing development program. Apart from tourists, the industry most affected by this program is the tourism industry. This is because several activities in the program always involve the tourism industry. In this case, the target groups in the tourism marketing development program are the wider community. The implementation of delivering information to tourists through offline tourism marketing is one of them, along with the implementation of the Tourism Information Center. The Tourism Information Center is a promotion facility to convert information about tourist attractions in Bandung and its surroundings. In practice, the tourism information center is located at *Husein Sastranegara* Airport, Bandung City Square, the Indonesian Railway Station, and *Paskal* Mall. The Tourism Information Center has experienced an increase in placement points. At first, the tourism information center only existed at one location point, namely Bandung Square, and starting in 2019 until now, it has increased to four location points.

Based on observations made in the field of the tourism information center in terms of the completeness of adequate infrastructure, the Information Center *Paskal* Mall has a special stand that is quite large and equipped with various facilities, such as a television that can show Bandung city tourism, the tourist who visit the tourist information center *Paskal* Mall can learn more about or get to know the tourism information center in *Paskal* Mall. It is different from the tourism information center in the other three places, which do not yet have a special stand and are equipped with adequate facilities, so tourists are not familiar with or understand the function of the presence of the tourism information center.

When executing the delivery of information directly at the four points of the tourism information center location, it is also equipped with information delivery media such as tourist destination books, tourism destination maps, and pamphlets that can support the delivery of information about tourism in Bandung City. This is useful so that tourists do not only get information from tourism information center employees; in the long term, tourists also get clearer information from books, pamphlets, and available tourism maps. Based on interviews conducted with informants, all forms of conveying information attempted by the Office of Culture and Tourism of Bandung City require assistance from other parties to carry out the delivery of this information.

The implementation of delivering information to tourists in an online tourism marketing development program is also carried out by utilizing the available information technology. The delivery of information to target groups carried out in tourism promotion activities utilizes platforms such as the YouTube tourism information center, the TikTok tourism information center, the Instagram of the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City, and the Instagram Tourism Information Center. Based on the interviews and observations, the available platforms for tourism promotion are good enough to create posts, videos, or other content with very attractive designs. If you look at the response of the public at large, what can be seen most is the influence of the utilization of this information technology. Based on the results of observations, data collection, and interviews conducted with informants, the research concludes that the dissemination of information by the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City has had a more positive impact through social media and other platforms. As for the direct delivery of information, there are still some obstacles. This requires support and cooperation from other parties to be able to assist in the implementation of this activity.

III. PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION ELEMENTS

Organizations or institutions with the function of implementing or assisting in the operation of a program are referred to as implementation elements. In this case, it is necessary to pay attention to the quantity and quality of the implementation elements. The quantity of implementation elements is related to the availability of sufficient human resources to carry out all matters in the existing program. Meanwhile, the quality of implementation elements is related to education, competence, skills, and experience in their fields. Both of these have a strong influence on the implementation of a program. In addition to adequate quality and quantity of human resources, the existing implementation elements are also required to understand how coordination is organized in the program being implemented and who is involved in playing a role in the program's implementation.

In the implementation of the Tourism Marketing Development Program, there are implementation actors or organizations responsible for running this program. The implementation organization is the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City, especially the Tourism Marketing Sector. The number of employees in the tourism marketing section consists of 8 state civil apparatus employees and 7 non-state civil apparatus employees, with details that can be seen in Figure 5 below:

Figure 5. Employees in the Tourism Marketing Sub-Section
Source: Research findings, 2022

The number of human resources in the marketing sector to carry out tourism marketing development programs is not insufficient; it can be seen that the tourism analysis section only consists of 2 people, whereas ideally, a minimum of 4 people would be in each section of the tourism marketing. Thus, this number does not match the tasks given because the marketing analysis section only has one staff member who takes care of various matters in the marketing analysis task. The lack of human resources is also felt by the

promotion section, which causes the tourism promotion section to be unable to divide activities into several teams. While the content they work on is quite varied, several tourism events are often held at the same time. Good coordination between implementation elements in the field of tourism marketing and organizing programs is also needed. The flow structure of the tourism marketing development program can be seen in the following figure 6:

Figure 6. Flowchart of the Tourism Marketing Development Program Structure
Source: Research findings, 2022

The Head of the Marketing Sector is the executor element in the implementation of the marketing development program. The program is divided into several activities held by each available section. If you look at the structure, there are 3 sections in the marketing sub-section. Each section has its activities. Ideally, this tourism marketing development program is carried out starting with a marketing analysis so that the results of the marketing analysis study are illustrated. From the marketing analysis study result, it can be seen what cooperation and promotions need to be carried out. But in practice, even though each section has carried out its duties properly, there is not always continuity between one section and another, such as the cycle, so in the end, tourism marketing does not have a correct and sustainable strategy.

Several parties, in addition to the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City, have helped in the implementation of this program. Following interviews with informants, it was explained that the actors involved in the marketing sector were categorized in the pentahelix element consisting of academia, government, community, media, and business. This can be seen in Figure 7 as follows:

Figure 7. Actors involved in assisting the implementation of tourism marketing development programs
Source: Research findings, 2022

Figure 7 depicts the five Penta helix elements: government, private/business, academia, media, and community/society. The fifth pentahelix element is involved in making tourism marketing development programs, in this case, the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City cannot act alone and needs other actors to assist in implementing this program. Based on the results of interviews with informants, there are several obstacles to implementation cooperation with tourism partners, one of which is the frequent occurrence of miscommunication, especially during online meetings. In addition, many tourism partners do not comply with the terms of the cooperation agreement. These agreements are frequently viewed as complicated by tourism partners, particularly the private sector and businesses, and the procedures are lengthy, making them inflexible and inefficient.

IV. ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS

The last component that needs to be considered in the program implementation process is environmental factors. Environmental factors are factors that can impact or be affected by the implementation of a program. This is because environmental factors can be considered barriers in society and need to be addressed in the program implementation process. These environmental factors can also be a driver or a hindrance to the program implementation process. In this case, tourism marketing development programs are heavily influenced by these environmental factors. In this case, the author will discuss the influence of social conditions and the physical environment (infrastructure and public transportation) as environmental factors that influence the tourism marketing development program at the Culture and Tourism Office of Bandung City.

One of the most influential factors is social conditions because many social issues occur and affect marketing development. social issues that arise such as homelessness, pickpockets, buskers, and the lack of cleanliness around tourist attractions. Thus, this becomes an inhibiting factor for tourism marketing because the social issues that occur can damage the tourism image of Bandung City.

In addition, the physical environment also influences tourist interest, especially in terms of infrastructure and public transportation. Bandung City's infrastructure is weak because it does not focus on building its infrastructure. If there are no funds to build new infrastructure, such as the lack of public toilets on the streets around *Braga Street* or *Bandung City Square*, at least maintain the existing infrastructure. Public awareness is also needed to maintain existing infrastructure. For public transportation, Bandung is very limited in terms of quantity and public transportation information; besides that, it still cannot overcome traffic jams, so tourism in Bandung City tends to be stagnant or saturated due to traffic jams, so there is not too much time that can be used for tourism. An example of comparison in terms of public transportation, road accessibility, and infrastructure that is quite good is in a city center location such as *Kiara Arta Park*. Meanwhile, for public transportation and road accessibility, what is not good are *Rosi Studio* and *Cigadung Batik Village*. Transportation or access is one of the elements that influence tourist visits. If a destination is to be promoted, it is necessary to look at the road access and transportation to the tourist destination, whether it is adequate or not. Marketing will be maximized if transportation access is improved. If it is not supported by good infrastructure and transportation, it will be difficult to market a tourism product.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research and discussion results of the implementation of marketing development programs to improve the image of tourism, they have not run optimally. In terms of achieving the target group aspect, although the dissemination of information that has been carried out has encountered several obstacles, the tourism promotion activities in this program have experienced quite good progress. However, there are some obstacles in other aspects. In aspects of their existence, such as budgets and facilities, they are still inadequate during the implementation of the promotional marketing development program. In the aspect of implementation elements, the implementation process still has problems in the form of a lack of quantity in employees who do not match the number of activities carried out in this program. There are still problems with cooperation with tourism partners, this is because they feel that the cooperation agreement procedure is not yet flexible. In terms of environmental factors, many social issues still occur in the surrounding community, thus affecting the implementation of this program. The implementation of the marketing development program requires assistance and support from various parties so that the implementation can run smoothly and improve the tourism image of Bandung City.

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